

**Along-strike variation of convergence rate and pre-existing weakness control
tearing of underthrusting Indian lithosphere beneath weak Tibetan plateau**

Qihua Cui¹, Zhong-Hai Li^{1,*}

¹Key Laboratory of Computational Geodynamics, College of Earth and Planetary Sciences,
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China

1. Datasets of all the models as summarized in Figure2 and Figure3.

Model-1.zip

Model-2.zip

Model-3.zip

Model-4.zip

Model-5.zip

Model-6.zip